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The praxis of gender-inclusive science education in engineering

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ABSTRACT

Many feminist science philosophers claim that gender-inclusive science education benefits women and men. However, most of these claims are theoretical propositions and lacking in empirical evidence. Therefore, this study attempts to examine these claims by exploring the learning experiences of male and female students in engineering project-based learning (PBL), a type of instruction found in gender-inclusive science education. This study was conducted in a PBL course offered by a power mechanical engineering department in a Taiwanese university. The project involved designing a mechanical equipment to accomplish a specific mission. This study involved 10 PBL groups of undergraduate freshmen with different gender compositions. Data collection involved recording videos of the whole processes of these 10 groups, related documents about the process such as their paper reports and project blueprints, and group interviews. There are three main findings. (a)The contextualized ontology, socially constructed epistemology, and multiple methodologies of this pedagogy have responded to recent developments in engineering. Therefore, this pedagogy expands and enriches the professional vision of both male and female students. (b)Traditional gender socialization and the male-dominated engineering culture are the main obstacles to gender-inclusive education. (c)Gender equality education is indispensable for rendering engineering education more gender inclusive

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